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Estimation of particulate matter from aerosol optical depth using collocated low-cost sensors and AERONET station in Lubango, Angola [†]

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Air pollution dynamics are still subject to many knowledge gaps, despite being recognized as a serious public health threat around the globe. In Africa, the existence of data is often rare and sparse, forcing the use of as many alternatives as possible, including remotely sensed data, reanalysis, and modeling approaches to fill the gaps. This study developed empirical models - linear, multivariate, and Bayesian regression models - for particulate matter (PM) estimation at three sizes (1, 2.5, and $10\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) from an Aerosol Optical Depth data source, at different wavelengths (340, 380, 440, and 500 nm). The observed root mean square error (RMSE) for the linear regression was 7.94, 18.10, and 22.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while the Bayesian showed errors of 7.86, 17.84, and 21.77 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM1, PM2.5, and PM10, respectively. The three-parameter Bayesian regression model showed better performance than the four-parameter multivariate regression model. This study has developed empirical models for the estimation of particulate matter using different wavelengths of aerosol optical depth. The result obtained can help local and national authorities to monitor air pollution using AOD measurements.

1 Introduction

Developing countries in the global south face an air pollution epidemic that exacerbates respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, increases transmission of infections, reduces visibility in transportation systems, drives climate change, and degradation of infrastructure¹⁻⁴. The sources of pollution vary widely from coun-

try to country and include transportation systems, biomass burning, industrial activities such as construction and manufacturing, and oil exploration activities such as gas flaring⁵. However, to achieve the sustainable development goals of reducing deaths and illnesses from air pollution (SDG3) and enhancing urban air quality (SDG11) in developing countries, there is a need for a robust, continuous, and accurate measurement of air pollution.

Countries, such as Angola, have challenges with particulate matter measurement due to the high cost of setting up, lack of awareness, and inadequate personnel to operate the systems. Despite the great need to fill the knowledge and spatial continuity gaps over the region, only recently have some data appeared in global or scientific publications⁶⁻¹⁰. Still, very little data has been gathered, and when it is available, it appears to be spatially and temporarily sparse. This reality forces researchers to use satellite measurement and reanalysis data to compensate for the gaps¹¹.

The Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET), a network of ground-based Sun photometers that measure atmospheric aerosol properties at a high temporal resolution over regional to global scales is available in some developing countries¹². Several studies have shown good agreement between AOD data from AERONET and some satellite measurements¹³. Measurements for aerosol optical depths (AOD) are readily available through satellite, reanalysis, or ground measurements in many places of the globe. However, as stated previously, particulate matter measurements are scarce and have low global spatial coverage.

There have been attempts to estimate particulate matter from aerosol optical depths or similar parameters¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Previous approaches considered AOD in connection with other atmospheric parameters such as humidity, boundary layer, and altitude. However, these measurements are not readily available in many locations or from satellite data. A linear relationship between AOD and PM2.5 has been proposed as follows:

$$PM2.5 = \mu AOD[x] + c \quad (1)$$

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where μ is the conversion factor between PM_{2.5} and AOD over the wavelength "x" and c is the intercept. Some studies have suggested that the ratio of PM_{2.5} to AOD can be used as a conversion factor¹⁷. Various authors have obtained different slope values for the linear regression between AOD and PM_{2.5} including 20.94 - 44.13 ($0.35 \leq r \leq 0.58$)¹⁸, 0.0067 - 0.03¹⁹, -3.097 ($r^2 = 0.36$)²⁰, 9.37 - 158.45²¹, and 0.57 - 0.82²². In a study by Kumar *et al.*²³, PM_{2.5} was estimated using a multilinear regression with AOD, mean sea level pressure, and relative humidity as predictors with a coefficient of variation between 0.61 and 0.81. Thus, it becomes clear that the conditions at a certain location store a specific combination that renders peculiar models for the estimation of Particulate Matter from AOD.

Given the knowledge gap in the central African region, this study aims to develop an empirical model - linear, multivariate, and Bayesian regression - for the estimation of particulate matter using AOD measurements at different wavelengths. It compared readings from an AERONET sensor and a co-located Low-Cost Sensor (LCS), looking for analytical relationships to infer Particulate Matter data from AOD data at different wavelengths. The study was carried out in southwestern Angola, using a programming environment to process the data, and specific values of the mathematical relationship between the measurements were found.

2 Study area and methodology

The present study was carried out with data collected at the Instituto Superior Politécnico Tundavala campus (13.44457, -14.95806), located on the outskirts of Lubango, a southwestern city of Angola. The Aerosol optical depth (AOD) data were obtained from the NASA Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET)²⁴, with Pre- and post-field calibration applied, automatically cloud cleared and manually inspected (Level 2.0 AOD, quality assured), for the "Lubango" station. The particulate matter data (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) was obtained from a NODE-S Clarity device, co-located with the AERONET sensor (Fig. 1). After cleaning and pre-processing, the resulting usable data comprised a data coverage of 9 months (18th May 2021 to 29th January 2022). All data management, statistical processing, and calculations were done in a programming environment, using a Google Colab notebook, connected to a GitHub repository from where the data was accessed.

The AERONET sunphotometer measures the loading of particles present in the entire column of the atmosphere, by measuring the quantity of light removed from a beam by scattering and/or absorption over its path, for a certain wavelength. The values depend on particle concentration, shape, size, chemical composition, location in the atmosphere, and wavelength of measurement²⁵. On the other hand, the Clarity NODE-S is a self-powered low-cost sensor model, that uses laser particle counter modules to determine the amount of particles and sizes. It contains a chamber with a determined air flow and infers the mass of particles in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ via a ratio between the scattering of energy and the known volume of the measuring chamber. The relationship between those measurements comes from the fact that both can be used in air quality applications, although significant dif-

Fig. 1 Clarity and AERONET sensors location at ISPTundavala Campus.

ferences exist between them. AOD represents the total particles in the atmosphere that produce a decay of the solar irradiation due to scattering and absorption by atmospheric elements such as air molecules, aerosols, water vapor, carbon dioxide, and ozone, while Particulate Matter refers specifically to dry mass particles present in the air, with or below a specific diameter. Thus, the use of regression can be (and has been) applied considering the assumption that, at a certain location, the AOD contains a fraction of the PM, and a linear relationship could be drawn containing the offset related to the other components present in the atmosphere.

Regarding the statical modeling, the Bayesian model selection allows for the optimal selection of the best combination of predictors $x_1 \dots, x_k$ that can be used to predict the state of a dependent variable, y . Bayesian methods provide a coherent framework for model comparison by evaluating the posterior probability of each candidate model given the observed data²⁶. The posterior model probability quantifies the plausibility of a model after accounting for both the "goodness of fit" to the data and the complexity of the model. Among the various Bayesian model selection criteria, the widely used Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) were computed. The AIC considers the maximum log-likelihood of the model along with a penalty term for the number of parameters, balancing goodness-of-fit and model complexity. Similarly, the BIC imposes a stricter penalty for model complexity, favoring more parsimonious models. Lower AIC and BIC values indicate a better trade-off between fit and simplicity. Furthermore, the Bayes factor, which represents the ratio of marginal likelihoods between two competing models, was calculated to quantify the strength of evidence in favor of one model over another. Thus, these Bayesian techniques facilitated the systematic evaluation and comparison of candidate models, enabling the selection of the most appropriate representation of the underlying data-generating process.

3 Results and discussion

The statistical properties of hourly AOD at different wavelengths and particulate matter at different sizes over the studied period

are presented in Fig. 2. The mean values of AOD at 500nm, 440nm, 380nm, and 340nm wavelength were found to be 0.38, 0.46, 0.55, and 0.62, respectively. This showed an increase from 0.38 at 500nm to 0.62 at 340nm, indicating stronger light extinction and particle interaction at shorter wavelengths. It implies that as the wavelength decreases, there is an increased scattering and absorption of atmospheric aerosols²⁷. For PM 1, PM 2.5, and PM 10, the mean values were found to be 11.83, 23.35, and 33.27 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. The values obtained for PM2.5 and PM10 exceeded the recommended annual values of 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively²⁸. The outliers suggest that the hourly values of PM2.5 and PM10 occasionally exceeded 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ ²⁹.

Fig. 2 Boxplot of hourly aerosol optical depth at different wavelengths (top) and particulate matter at different sizes (bottom). Mean values are represented by white circles.

The relationship between each of the AOD wavelengths and particulate matter, using linear regression, can be seen in Fig. 3. In the linear regression analysis between PM1 and AOD at different wavelengths, the slope (10.62 - 17.09) was found to decrease with decreasing wavelength with a correlation between 0.43 and 0.44. Similar patterns were observed across the three particulate matter sizes. At PM2.5, the slope values (19.47 - 32.26) increased compared to PM1 but the correlation was a little lower. These slope values were lower¹⁸, higher^{19,20,22}, and within the range²¹ of studies in other regions. PM10 had the highest slope values of the three sizes, ranging from 25.64 to 42.7. The positive slope signifies that an increase in AOD would also imply an increase in particulate matter in the atmosphere. A lower value of slope indicates that there is a smaller increase in particulate matter at that wavelength. Hence, we can infer that there is a higher detection of particulate matter at a higher wavelength compared to lower wavelengths. The intercept values were computed as 5.245 ± 0.0331 , 11.07 ± 0.071 , and 17.06 ± 0.123 for PM1, PM2.5, and PM10, respectively.

The resulting empirical expressions for particulate matter using aerosol optical depths at four wavelengths, for both linear and Bayesian regressions, are found in Table 1, which uncovered a nuanced relationship between the aerosol optical depth and particulate matter characteristics at the location under consideration. In each of these two models, the coefficient represents the contribution or component of the AOD wavelength needed to make a prediction of the corresponding particulate matter size. In the

Table 1 Linear and Bayesian regression statistics for particulate matter modeling and their error evaluation.

Parameter ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Model	500 nm	440 nm	380 nm	340 nm	intercept	rmse	BIC
PM 1.0	Linear Regression	-403.94	486.10	-49.86	-58.77	8.37	7.94	-1594.90
PM 2.5		-998.41	1226.31	-82.02	-207.07	19.28	18.10	-469.10
PM 10.0		-1283.14	1581.11	-92.13	-281.08	27.71	22.11	-195.96
PM 1.0	Bayesian model	-383.47	435.88	-78.51		8.28	7.86	0.04
PM 2.5		-964.73	1143.70	-239.55		19.12	17.84	0.04
PM 10.0		-1245.31	1488.31	-317.55		27.53	21.77	0.04

linear regression analysis, the contributions of each component of AOD were observed to be negative except 440 nm which had a positive contribution. These negative contributions were found to decrease with the increase in PM size, while the positive contribution at 440 nm increased with increasing PM size. The intercept, which represents the offset in the model, was also observed to increase with increasing particulate matter size. This is expected as it corresponds to the particulate matter size when the predictors have zero values, which is expected to contain higher mass. The errors obtained were in the range $7.94 - 22.11 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $7.86 - 21.77 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for linear and Bayesian regressions, respectively. PM1 observed the lowest error for both models, while PM10 resulted in the highest error margins, meaning that the resulting models showed for PM1 an average deviation of model predictions from actual particulate matter concentrations of approximately $7.86 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ from measured values, while PM10 could deviate up to $22.11 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This result highlights that there are still challenges for precisely measuring particulate matter to bring the error to reasonable standardized levels, such as the WHO Air Quality Guidelines. Moreover, the observed tendency of the BIC values also agrees with the root mean square evaluation. The Bayesian regression approach showed more refined coefficient adjustments and consistently lower error rates when compared to the linear regression model. Specifically, the Bayesian regression approach utilizes only three AOD components - 500 nm, 440 nm, and 380 nm, with comparatively better performance.

Complex processes are involved in the generation of particulate matter at any given location including atmospheric and tropospheric conditions, human activity, and regional influence. Furthermore, there are intrinsic inaccuracies in the measurement of both AOD and particulate matter. Several factors can affect the estimation of PM from AOD including decomposition of AOD by aerosol types, mismatch in spatial-temporal resolution, collocation and integration of AOD and PM data, and control for spatial-temporal structure in the statistical model³⁰. For instance, sun spectrophotometer measurements cover only daytime pollution, however, nighttime pollution often evolves into daytime occurrences. Furthermore, the approach in this study did not consider external variables such as humidity, temperature, or boundary layer dynamics, with associated errors, rendering it a more simplified approach and making the accurate estimation of particulate matter from AOD subjected to inherent errors.

4 Conclusion

This study aimed to develop robust empirical models to estimate PM1, PM2.5, and PM10 concentrations based on AOD values at various wavelengths. It utilized data from a Clarity low-cost sensor and an AERONET station in Lubango, Angola. The method-

Fig. 3 Linear regression plots between the different particulate matter sizes and aerosol optical depths.

ology employed linear regression and Bayesian regression techniques to explore the relationships between AOD and particulate matter. The resulting model showed that, for the study region, AOD values increased at shorter wavelengths, which indicates a greater scattering by fine particles and shows agreement with most examples in the literature from other parts of the globe regarding a positive slope between AOD and PM. The mean concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ significantly exceeded recommended limits, with occasional extreme values observed. The linear regression models demonstrated a stronger correlation between higher AOD wavelengths and increased PM concentrations. On the other hand, the Bayesian regression showed superior performance by utilizing fewer AOD components and achieving lower error rates. The Root mean square error (RMSE) showed variations higher than recommended PM levels, which may pose an uncertainty even if levels are found to be low, highlighting the need to refine these PM prediction models further, probably by considering other factors and processes in the prediction analysis. This study strongly emphasizes the complexity of estimating PM due to various factors, including atmospheric dynamics, measurement inaccuracies, and temporal-spatial mismatches. While the developed models improve the estimation of PM concentrations, it is worth noting that they do not account for external variables such as humidity and boundary layer effects. Thus, it remains im-

portant to continue gathering location-specific information and studying these relationships, to fill the knowledge gaps and allow future inter-comparisons and a better understanding of the AOD vs PM relationships.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: E. E. S. Pires. Methodology: S. Ogunjo. Data curation: E. E. S. Pires, S. Ogunjo. Investigation: O. Taiwo, O. Olaniyan. Writing – original draft: E. E. S. Pires, S. Ogunjo, O. Taiwo, O. Olaniyan.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

The AERONET data used in this study is openly available for download from the AERONET Download site from the link: https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/webtool_aod_v3.html. The Clarity data, which cannot be made available due to proprietary rights, can be requested from the corresponding author.

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